

Short communication

A multidisciplinary perspective on the role of plastic pollution in the triple planetary crisis

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ABSTRACT

In this perspective paper, we discuss the negative impacts of plastics and associated chemicals on the triple planetary crisis of environmental pollution, climate change and biodiversity loss from a multidisciplinary perspective. Plastics are part of the pollution crisis, threatening ecosystems and human health. They also impact climate change and accelerate biodiversity loss; in this, they aggravate the triple planetary crisis. We analyze the scientific state-of-the-art to identify critical knowledge gaps regarding the life cycle, release, fate, exposure, hazard and governance of plastics and associated chemicals, as well as links to climate change and biodiversity loss. Based on the outcome, we derive key research needs for a comprehensive hazard assessment of plastics and associated chemicals, amongst others, to address the largely missing regulation of plastic additives and in-use plastics. We offer a holistic perspective bridging disciplinary expertise from natural and social sciences to achieve effective plastic governance and risk management of plastics and associated chemicals that protect the Earth, its ecosystems and human health from the plastics crisis.

1. Setting the scene

This perspective article focuses on plastics as part of the pollution crisis and their role in aggravating the triple planetary crisis. In this context, plastic pollution comprises the polymeric base materials (macromolecules that make up the bulk polymer), including non-polymerized residues (monomers, oligomers) from polymer production, in combination with associated chemicals, such as intentionally added compounds to yield specific properties (additives and processing aids), and non-intentionally added chemicals such as reaction by-products and impurities. Specifically, we do not cover rubber-based materials such as tire wear material or liquid polymer formulations.

Synthetic polymers are flexible materials that are currently irreplaceable – yet their wide use has led to the presence of plastics and associated chemicals in the most remote and pristine areas of the Earth (Materić et al., 2022). Recent multi-author estimates have shown that the global emissions of plastics and associated chemicals will continue to rise unless extensive actions are taken to limit emissions (Borrelle et al., 2020; Lau et al., 2020). In light of the recognition of plastic pollution as a threat to planetary boundaries (Jahnke et al., 2017; Arp et al., 2021;

Persson et al., 2022; Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2022a; Scientists' Coalition for an Effective Plastics Treaty, 2024) and due to the ubiquity, persistence and irreversibility of plastic pollution in many global regions (MacLeod et al., 2021), we need to urgently and substantially reduce plastic production and emissions. In particular for humans, in-use plastics, e.g., in the indoor environment, represent an additional exposure pathway to micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) and associated chemicals (Abb et al., 2009).

Hence, both plastics released into the environment and in-use pose hazards to ecosystems and human health. In this, plastics represent a substantial fraction of the global pollution crisis that is challenging to quantify due to the material's enormous complexity, including polymer and additive types, particles' size, shape and chemical composition. Furthermore, in the environment, plastics are subject to diverse weathering processes that change the material's properties, promoting disintegration, hence altering its transport, fate and potential to elicit effects directly (as particles) or indirectly (via leached chemicals). The persistence of plastics further impacts their fate and potential to elicit adverse effects. As certain hazards for wildlife and humans increase with decreasing particle size, microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs) are

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important to consider. In addition, plastic-associated chemicals, including additives, non-polymerized mono- and oligomers, metals, processing aids, and non-intentionally added substances, are highly diverse, with a substantial fraction known to be hazardous (UN Environment Programme, 2023; Wagner et al., 2024).

The pollution crisis accompanies the crises of climate change and biodiversity loss, threatening the Earth and humanity as the triple planetary crisis (UNFCCC, 2022). These crises are closely interlinked, and the related impacts of plastics have been outlined (MacLeod et al., 2021; Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2022a). There are globally active panels bringing together solid scientific expertise for two of the crises: Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (UN IPCC, 2023) and Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2020). Contrarily, a corresponding global panel on pollution and waste is, to date, lacking (Wang et al., 2021; Brack et al., 2022). Global actors currently negotiate international legally binding instruments, specifically for plastic pollution (UN Environment Programme, 2022), i.e., the Global Plastics Treaty, and more generally for chemicals, waste and pollution prevention (UN Environment Programme, 2024). While the processes hold tremendous promise, the outcomes remain uncertain due to powerful vested interests (Wagner, 2024).

We shed light on the state of knowledge in diverse fields of science, contrasting what is known and what we need to know regarding the contribution of plastics and associated chemicals to the triple planetary crisis. From a systematic literature search, we derive future research directions that help close pressing knowledge gaps to pave the way

towards substantially reduced production and emissions.

2. State of knowledge regarding the role of plastics in the triple planetary crisis

We aimed to achieve a systems understanding of plastics and partly associated chemicals to estimate their role in the triple planetary crisis of pollution, climate change and biodiversity loss. The results of the related extensive literature search are mapped in Fig. 1. For pollution, we cover the entire life cycle and release, fate, exposure and hazards to humans and wildlife. For climate change and biodiversity loss, we focus on three major aspects each, whereas a more comprehensive overview of impact pathways is discussed in Villarrubia-Gómez et al. (2022a). In addition, a summary of the results is presented in Table 1, and the detailed results are given in Schmidt et al. (2024).

Our bibliographic analysis revealed the numbers of publications concerning plastic pollution in the context of the triple planetary crisis, which we used to identify knowledge-rich vs. knowledge-scarce areas (Graphical abstract, Fig. 1, Table 1). In the main categories, the literature search showed that plastics have primarily been investigated as part of the pollution crisis (17463 publications), whereas analyses focusing on the context of climate change and biodiversity loss (1279 vs. 652 publications) are not that extensive yet. Furthermore, we covered governance, which gave a similar picture on the number of publications in the context of pollution, climate change and biodiversity loss. Where relevant, we also covered plastic-associated chemicals for which relatively few publications exist (Table 1). The outcomes are discussed in

Fig. 1. An overview of the impacts of plastics on the triple planetary crisis, focusing on climate change (top), pollution (center), and biodiversity loss (bottom). For the plastics life cycle and release, mass-based numbers are given (Geyer, 2020a, covering 1950–2017). In contrast, for fate, exposure, hazard, regulation and governance as well as the key aspects of climate change and biodiversity loss, the assessment was based on the number of publications identified in a Web of Science search as summarized in Table 1 and detailed in Schmidt et al. (2024).

Table 1

Summary of our literature search, detailing the numbers of publications for diverse fields, and the numbers and fractions of reviews amongst them. The sum of papers in the subcategories is not equal to the total number of papers in the main categories, as publications may cover more than one subcategory. A detailed overview of the search results is provided by Schmidt et al. (2024).

Topic	# Publications	# Reviews	% Reviews
Plastics and Climate Change	1279	177	13.8
Plastics and Greenhouse Gas Emissions	1112	160	14.4
Plastics and Carbon Cycle	141	20	14.2
Plastics and Albedo	57	2	3.5
Plastics and Pollution	17,463	2431	13.9
Plastics Fate	7636	1116	14.6
Plastics Exposure	14,062	2022	14.4
Plastics Hazard	8018	1642	20.5
Hazard of Associated Chemicals (Human + Wildlife)	1987	434	21.8
Plastics and Biodiversity Loss	652	96	14.7
Plastics and Transport	125	15	12.0
Plastics and Habitat Change	452	48	10.6
Plastics and Toxicity	207	55	26.6
Plastics and Governance			
Plastics, Governance and Climate Change	290	66	22.8
Plastics, Governance and Pollution	4002	755	18.9
Plastics, Governance and Biodiversity	109	39	35.8
Plastics, Governance and Associated Chemicals	96	24	25.0

detail in the following section.

3. Role of plastics in the triple planetary crisis

3.1. Leaky life cycle

Since the 1950s, approximately 9200 million tons (MT) of primary plastics have been mass-produced (Geyer, 2020b), almost exclusively based on fossil fuel feedstocks (for details, see chapter 3.5). The plastic life cycle can be broadly divided into three stages, plastics that (i) are currently in use, (ii) have been officially treated at the end of their life cycle (defined as recycled, incinerated, or disposed of in landfills), and (iii) have leaked into the environment as mismanaged waste. Discarded plastics including the mismanaged fraction sum up to 5300 MT. Globally, $\frac{1}{3}$ - $\frac{1}{2}$ of the plastic waste is considered as mismanaged, including open, informal dumps and littering. This fraction is susceptible to transport via wind and water and leads to wide environmental spread. Assessments of plastic pollution and transport often consider mismanaged waste as a primary source of plastics to the environment. Other pathways through which plastics leak into the environment, e.g., catastrophic events such as tsunamis and floods, are by far less studied and understood. Currently, an estimated 2900 MT of plastics are in use, comprising 2700 MT of primary plastics and 200 MT of recycled material. These may end up in the environment through accidental losses and weathering, but they also represent a major pathway for human exposure during use, particularly indoors. Packaging comprises the largest fraction of plastics production, followed by building/construction materials and textiles. Products such as insulation material, cables, or pipes might be in use for decades, whereas the use phase for textiles is usually years, and for packaging, it might not be longer than days to weeks. During these times of use, weathering, abrasion, and the generation of leachates are the most relevant exposure pathways.

While data on polymer production is available, production, characteristics and use of additives are largely undisclosed. It is estimated that

plastics contain on average 7 % of additives by mass, indicating that a total amount of around 640 MT of additives have been produced so far. The nature and amount of additives can vary substantially depending on the polymer type and ultimate product (Hansen, 2013; Hahladakis et al., 2018; Groh et al., 2019; Geyer, 2020b; Wiesinger et al., 2021), representing a major challenge for risk management and recyclability.

3.2. Environmental weathering factors impact plastics' fate

Both plastic items of different sizes and chemical leaching contribute to the pollution crisis. Weathering plays a major role in this context since it impacts the rate and degree of liberation of small particles and free chemicals from macroplastics. Our literature survey showed that 7475 publications addressed the weathering, aging and fragmentation of MPs, whereas NPs were less covered (1274 publications). Notably, in emerging research fields, the fraction of reviews usually is high, whereas regular research papers emerge over time, resulting in lower fractions of reviews. Here, the small fraction of reviews indicated a relatively mature, knowledge-rich area (Fig. 1).

Complex environmental weathering makes plastics a constantly moving target: Leaching of chemicals can change the plastics' properties, e.g. fostering surface embrittlement, increasing the surface area-to-volume ratio and hence leaching rates, as well as shedding of a multitude of irregularly shaped MNPs. Weathering also impacts wettability and, consequently, buoyancy. On land, UV irradiation has a strong impact on the weathering of plastic items, as does mechanical stress if transported by wind over rough surfaces. In water, immediate coverage with organic molecules fosters the development of biofilms, giving protection from UV radiation but also fostering biodegradation (Rummel et al., 2017). Biofilms can increase the bulk density and thus facilitate sinking; additionally, they make it more challenging for organisms to distinguish MNPs from prey. Furthermore, organisms can impact the fate of plastics, including microbial degradation, fragmentation when passing the organisms' digestive tract, and cluster formation with fecal pellets that fosters sinking (Pérez-Guevara et al., 2021). Several polymers have been shown to be degraded by bacteria or fungi, but rates under environmental conditions are very slow. Fragmentation of MNPs can even take place through the digestive activity of amphipods (Mateos-Cárdenas et al., 2020) or rotifers (Zhao et al., 2024). Future research should consider weathering, leaching, and fragmentation while following ongoing efforts to harmonize methods for sampling, analysis, and data reporting to improve comparability.

3.3. Exposure of wildlife and humans to plastics and associated chemicals

Wildlife becomes exposed to MNPs and associated chemicals across environmental compartments, including the marine, freshwater, and terrestrial (mainly agricultural) environments, the atmosphere and the cryosphere. Characterizing exposure pathways and the extent of exposure is crucial for better understanding the hazards and impacts of MNPs related to biodiversity loss (for details, see chapter 3.6). Plastics in the marine environment have been studied the most (9706 publications for MPs, 1103 for NPs, Fig. 1), since MPs were first identified there (Thompson et al., 2004), and NPs only became detectable recently. The research on marine MNPs initiated an emphasis on freshwater systems (lakes and rivers, 4370 vs. 492 publications for MPs vs. NPs), moving from the marine sinks to the terrestrial sources (4403 vs. 734 papers, Rochman, 2018). Regarding new research trends, scientists have only started focusing on the cryosphere (499 vs. 74 publications) and air (1549 vs. 309 publications), and the lack of maturity of research on MNPs in the atmosphere is mirrored in the high fractions of reviews (24.7 % for MPs and 36.2 % for NPs, Fig. 1). Our literature search also showed that NPs have generally been understudied to date, supported by a higher fraction of reviews compared to MPs (e.g., for soils, 20.4 % for MPs vs. 35.6 % for NPs, Fig. 1).

Wildlife exposure to plastics occurs mainly from the lost or

mismanaged fractions, but also to associated chemicals liberated from in-use and mismanaged plastics. Specific knowledge gaps comprise exposure from air, the track record of MNPs in the cryosphere, specific MNP loads for most environmental compartments, and concentrations of leaching chemicals and transformation products. Most publications consider compartments separately, and little information is available regarding plastic transfer between them (Allen et al., 2022). Wildlife exposure is closely linked to human exposure via consumption of drinking water and food, e.g., fish, seafood, crops and vegetables. Future research should investigate MNPs in knowledge-scarce areas like the cryosphere and atmosphere; the latter needs to be addressed urgently in order to assess long-range transport and the relevance of the inhalation uptake pathway for air-breathing biota including humans. Information on the size distribution of MNPs is rarely available (Fraissinet et al., 2024), but essential to develop better numerical models for MNP transport and our understanding of their sinks and availability for biological uptake. Our knowledge is also limited regarding exposure to plastic-associated chemicals, but modeling (Gouin et al., 2011; Koelmans et al., 2016) and experimental work (Rummel et al., 2016) indicate that the impact of chemicals from plastics is small compared to that from food.

Given their wide use, human exposure to plastics and associated chemicals is ubiquitous. Exposure can occur through ingestion, inhalation and, to a lesser extent, via the skin (Ramsperger et al., 2023), followed by translocation into the circulation systems and peripheral tissues (Zhu et al., 2024). Of these, the relevance of ingestion has partly been assessed, whereas information on inhalation is largely missing. Large differences in human exposure can be expected, since certain occupations or geographical regions might have highly elevated exposure levels. Certain plastics have been well studied, e.g., polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polyethylene (PE), whereas others are to date poorly covered. Still, there is little understanding of real-life exposure to small MPs (<10 µm) and NPs from different exposure pathways as only few case studies are available (Kirchsteiger et al., 2023; Kau et al., 2024).

3.4. Plastics and associated chemicals imply a hazard for wildlife and humans

For impacts on wildlife and humans our literature survey resulted in similar numbers of papers, for MP 4632 vs. 4274 publications, and for NP 1153 vs. 1094 publications. However, for humans the fraction of reviews (25.2 % for MP and 32.8 % for NP) was higher than for wildlife (20.4 % and 25.4 %, respectively). This higher percentage indicates that the exposure to plastics was initially perceived as a hazard for the environment, whereas research only recently started to focus on human health. Similar to other areas there were roughly four times more studies on MPs than NPs.

Regarding the effects of associated chemicals, only few studies were found for wildlife, with 532 papers on effects of MP-associated chemicals, and 105 on NP-associated chemicals. The fractions of reviews were 27.8 %, and 44.3 %, respectively, indicating a relatively immature research field. Overall, hazardous effects are considered a key driver of biodiversity loss, highlighting the related research needs. In humans, the effects of associated chemicals were more frequently studied (1429 publications), with the largest fraction addressing plastic-associated chemicals in general, 369 focusing on effects of MP- and 105 on NP-associated chemicals. The fractions of reviews were 19.7 %, 36.0 % and 47.6 %, respectively. Notably, most studies only investigated individual chemicals in isolation; contrarily, the investigation of complex leachates and possible combined effects of particles and chemicals represent research needs.

3.4.1. Impacts on wildlife

Hazard characterization for MNPs has mainly been done in marine and freshwater laboratory studies with single species, and

predominantly for polystyrene (PS) (de Sá et al., 2018; Bucci et al., 2020). For several species, no adverse effects were observed despite very high exposure concentrations. It is generally assumed that the smaller the plastic particles are, the higher the likelihood of transfer across biological membranes, and the more adverse effects in organisms occur. However, three meta-analyses focusing on water organisms (Burns and Boxall, 2018; Yang and Nowack, 2020; Takeshita et al., 2022) concluded that the toxicity of NPs was somewhat lower than for MPs.

Whereas the hazardous effects of plastics for aquatic vertebrate populations (e.g., fish) are well understood, much less is known about (semi-)terrestrial species (e.g., birds) (Blettler et al., 2020). Recent studies with model aquatic invertebrates and environmentally relevant MNP concentrations have shown increased gene expression of antioxidant enzymes, increased production of reactive oxygen species or a weakened intestinal barrier (Prata et al., 2021). Distinguishing between direct (physical) effects induced by the plastic particles and indirect (chemical) effects stemming from plastic-associated chemicals is in many cases challenging. To this end, more control experiments with comparable natural particles are needed. For effect assessment of plastic-associated chemicals, it needs to be considered that many of them are poorly water-soluble (Wiesinger et al., 2021). Therefore, their testing at relevant concentrations in aquatic media requires a dedicated experimental design. Extrapolation from observations with laboratory leachates to real environments is challenging.

Research needs include impacts from airborne plastics and associated chemicals (e.g., hazard in lung-breathing organisms, relevance of atmospheric deposition on plants) and impacts on organisms inhabiting the cryosphere and soil. Other stressors need to be considered in combination with MNP exposure, such as climate change-related altered temperature and moisture regimes, starvation, invasive species, diseases, and parasites.

3.4.2. Impacts on human health

As indicated above, we are just beginning to understand the effects and underlying mechanisms of MNPs and associated chemicals on human health, as their interactions in the human body are very complex and target different cell types across tissues. From reasonable coverage of data on MPs in fish, seafood and drinking water, human uptake via ingestion can be estimated, whereas for NPs data just start to emerge (Fraissinet et al., 2024). Contrarily, more data on MNPs in the atmosphere are needed to characterize the uptake via inhalation and resulting impacts.

MNPs have been associated with adverse effects on the reproductive, immune, nervous and cardiovascular systems (Li et al., 2023), but there is a lack of detailed mechanistic knowledge, as well as on the relevant physicochemical properties responsible for the adverse effects. Furthermore, most studies used commercially available PS particles (Wieland et al., 2024), which do not reflect realistic exposure scenarios. Some primary findings about the impacts of MNPs on human health have recently been reported: One study found MNPs, i.e., PE, in the carotid arteries (i.e., those supplying the brain) of close to half of the study participants and derived increased risks of adverse downstream incidents (Marfella et al., 2024). Other recent work highlighted the role of MNPs in cell migration and distribution during cancer cell division (Brynzak-Schreiber et al., 2024). Such singular studies call for additional research to substantiate findings and better elucidate the impacts of plastics and associated chemicals on human health and their underlying mechanisms.

Of particular concern is also the release of plastic-associated chemicals into peripheral tissues following particle uptake via ingestion or inhalation. Although some characteristics of the modes-of-action (i.e., molecular effects that affect the function of cells or tissues resulting from exposure) of plasticizers have been identified, there is still a notable lack of mechanistic data due to the large diversity of additives and related chemicals (Hahladakis et al., 2018; Groh et al., 2019; Wiesinger et al., 2021; UN Environment Programme, 2023; Wagner et al., 2024). Recent

studies with leachates from everyday plastics revealed strong effects towards receptors and gene expression (McPartland et al., 2024; Stevens et al., 2024). However, understanding the effects and hazards posed by realistic plastics and associated chemicals is crucial for identifying adverse effects and for developing sound regulatory measures to protect human health.

3.5. Plastic pollution has an impact on climate change

Core aspects regarding the impact of plastic pollution on climate change include greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, impacts on the carbon cycle and on the albedo (Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2022a). Throughout their life cycle, plastics contribute to anthropogenic GHG emissions. About 99 % of plastic production is currently based on fossil fuel feedstocks (Hamilton and Feit, 2019). For the production of one metric ton of plastic resin about 1.9 metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalents (t CO₂e) are emitted (Hamilton and Feit, 2019). Incineration releases about 2.9 t CO₂e per metric ton of plastic. When accounting for the offset of energy of an estimated 2 t CO₂e, the net GHG emission from incineration is 0.9 t CO₂e. Life cycle GHG emissions from plastics currently contribute about 2–4 % of global annual GHG emissions (Hamilton and Feit, 2019; Zheng and Suh, 2019). The plastic industry estimated at least a 10 % contribution to total “global warming potential” if its relative contribution to other material groups is included (STAP, 2011; Stoett and Vince, 2019). If plastic production continues to grow at current rates, these fractions will increase. Incineration, in particular, postulated as an effective means to reduce mismanaged plastic waste, contributes to the climate crisis. Estimates of production-related GHG emissions do not so far include additive production.

Weathering of plastics can release greenhouse gases, e.g., methane and ethylene (Royer et al., 2018). However, the significance for global GHG emissions has yet to be explored. Plastics-related GHG emissions have received considerable attention in the scientific literature with 1112 publications. Beyond GHG emissions, plastics-related climate impacts can occur after being released into the environment. Plastics can also interfere with the marine carbon cycle by affecting the biological carbon pump and reducing the efficiency of carbon sequestration by marine organisms (Wright et al., 2013), amongst others limiting transfer of nutrients to the sea floor (MacLeod et al., 2021). Deposition on snow and ice can influence the albedo, increasing the absorption of radiation and contributing to global warming (Geilfus et al., 2019). Both the impacts on plastics on the carbon cycle and albedo have not been well studied yet (141 and 57 publications, respectively). Studies examining the impact of plastic pollution on marine carbon sequestration are emerging, however, knowledge gaps exist as the interactions between plastic pollution and marine carbon sinks, which are complex and multifaceted, involving various ecological processes.

3.6. Plastic pollution has an impact on biodiversity loss

The impact of plastic pollution on biodiversity includes toxicity, alteration of habitats and ecosystems, and species translocation (“rafting”, involving transport of invasive species or pathogens) (Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2022a). The focus of many related studies is on MPs, but macroplastics also have an impact on biodiversity as new habitat, nesting material, by exerting indirect effects such as entanglement and facilitating rafting across habitats (Barnes and Milner, 2005; Goldstein et al., 2014). Most studies addressing the impact of plastic pollution on biodiversity loss have focused on single or few species in distinct geographical habitats such as lagoons or mangroves. In controlled laboratory studies, MNP effects may be small, but can still become critical in real environments at hot spots or when combined with other (multiple) stressors such as starvation, parasites, and predation. In some areas, plastic pollution has reached effect thresholds, e.g., in vulnerable ecosystems such as coral reefs (Lamb et al., 2018). Evidence for impacts of MNPs on biodiversity loss exists for microbial communities (Hu et al.,

2019; Agathokleous et al., 2021). The few long-term studies available for MNP effects on macroinvertebrates (e.g., snails, worms) (Redondo-Hasselerharm et al., 2020) and micro-/meioinvertebrates (e.g., water fleas) (Rauchschtalbe et al., 2022) suggest subtle effects on population abundance and diversity that did not increase with higher dose.

Alternative terms to “biodiversity”, such as “species richness”, “taxa” and “community composition” are used more prevalently in the scientific literature, in particular in studies on biofilm composition on plastics. Overall, the individual impact of plastics on biodiversity (i.e., isolated from other pollutants) is not well established. Most studies addressed the habitat impact on biodiversity (452), while fewer addressed the related impact of toxicity and rafting (207 vs. 125 studies, respectively). Although some studies on behavioral effects of MP exposure are available, no links to impacts on biodiversity loss have been identified yet. Biodiversity loss in microbial and planktonic communities implies a close connection to climate change resulting from the impact of these organisms on biogeochemical cycles (Amanesh et al., 2023). Climate change effects on biodiversity through temperature shifts may be amplified or weakened by plastic pollution, especially regarding animals with temperature-controlled sex ratios (Hawkes et al., 2007; Fuentes et al., 2023).

4. Future research directions for effective plastic governance

Plastic pollution has profound environmental, political, and social implications beyond its physical presence, influencing and influenced by economic systems, regulatory frameworks, and cultural practices (Gabrys et al., 2013). Despite extensive use and accumulation following its initial proliferation, plastic governance literature has primarily focused on plastic waste and pollution (4002 publications) (Villarrubia-Gómez et al. 2022b), with substantially less attention paid to its complexity, including the hazards from in-use plastics and associated chemicals (96 publications). While there is a growing body of governance scholarship on MPs (European Commission and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2019) and NPs (1374 and 248 publications respectively), holistic considerations of the full life cycle of plastics, both in-use and waste, as well as macroplastics and MNPs, are missing. Governance literature is beginning to link the role of plastics as part of the pollution crisis with climate change (290 publications) (e.g., Stoett and Vince, 2019; Tang, 2023), but connections to biodiversity loss remain fragmented (109 publications) and lack a holistic character that investigates indirect contributions through social narratives and practices of convenience culture. Effective plastics governance should be closely aligned with climate and biodiversity goals at national and international levels, and strive to reduce production, prevent environmental leakage, increase responsible reuse, and ensure recyclability by simplification of polymers and associated chemicals (Brander et al., 2024). A guiding question for interdisciplinary governance research should therefore be: What are the limits, uncertainties, opportunities and barriers for sustainable plastic management in line with international climate and biodiversity targets and governance?

Despite current knowledge and consensus to act, international discussions often focus on end-of-life recycling over reduce-and-reuse strategies (Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2022a), and existing legal frameworks fail to limit plastic production to essential uses (Hsu et al., 2021; OECD, 2022; Brander et al., 2024). Collaborative research is therefore crucial between environmental, social and cultural sciences to develop sustainable plastic futures, supported by interdisciplinary platforms like the Coalition for an Effective Plastics Treaty (<https://ikhapp.org/scientistscoalition/>) and the Scientific Advice Mechanism to the European Commission (<https://scientificadvice.eu/>). Future initiatives could provide transdisciplinary spaces for scientists and citizens to jointly inform policymakers, ensuring democratic processes and socially and politically accepted solutions (Blum, 2024). Therefore, further guiding research questions should include: How can sustainable plastic governance be applied at multiple scales? What could sustainable plastic use

mean for trade, development and culture?

5. Concluding remarks

Given that plastics and associated chemicals aggravate the triple planetary crisis as discussed above and in the scientific literature (Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2022a; Scientists' Coalition for an Effective Plastics Treaty, 2024), we call for the urgent reduction of this negative impact to the largest possible extent. While plastic pollution forms part of the pollution crisis, there are multiple factors that aggravate the crises of climate change (e.g., via GHG emissions) and biodiversity loss (e.g., via altered habitats). These wide-ranging negative impacts of in-use and mismanaged plastics as well as associated chemicals may be reduced by regulating plastic additives on the one hand and in-use plastics on the other hand. Furthermore, we stress the imperative to avoid limiting the assessment of plastics and associated chemicals as an isolated threat, but rather consider MNPs as closely interlinked with the triple planetary crisis and beyond, being one stressor amongst many in the multiple stressor context. We strongly advocate to consider the interaction of plastics and associated chemicals with other pollutants as well as mutual interactions and potential amplifications with the crises of climate change and biodiversity loss, to ensure implementation of adequate global measures to protect the Earth, its ecosystems and human health from the plastics crisis.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Christian Schmidt: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dana Kühnel:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Dušan Materić:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jessica Stubenrauch:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Kristin Schubert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Anran Luo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Katrin Wendt-Potthoff:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Annika Jahnke:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data available online on Zenodo, Schmidt et al. (2024).

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